

D 2.2 Optimized Initial field for improved seasonal forecasting

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DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
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OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	X

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the development and evaluation of a data assimilation (DA) system for the Baltic Sea within the MOIRAI project. A Data Assimilation (DA) reanalysis for 2024 demonstrates that the MOIRAI-DA reduces SST errors relative to the reference run and outperforms or matches BALMFC operational products, while also correctly reproducing sea-ice extent for the 2023–2024 winter season. Free-run experiments initialized on the 1st of January 2025 confirm that the MOIRAI-DA initial conditions provide accurate temperature (cRMSE < 0.6°C) and salinity (cRMSE < 1.0 psu) over five months when validated against Argo float observations, demonstrating the suitability of the MOIRAI-DA restart files as starting conditions for seasonal and decadal predictability studies.

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Acronyms

SST	Sea Surface Temperature
DA	Data Assimilation
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
LESTKF	Localized Error Subspace Transform Kalman Filter
BALMFC	the BALtic sea Monitoring and Forecasting Centre
PDAF	the Parallel Data Assimilation Framework
VOTO	Voice Of The Ocean foundation
NRT	Near Real Time
MYP	Multi-Year Products
SSH	Sea Surface Height
ICES	the International Council of Exploitation of the Sea
cRMSE	centered Root Mean Square Error
REF	REFerence run

1. Introduction

Accurate initialization of ocean models is one of the central challenges in seasonal-to-decadal climate prediction. The ocean, owing to its large thermal inertia and capacity to store and redistribute heat, constitutes the primary source of predictability on timescales of months to years. Unlike the atmosphere, which loses memory of its initial state within days to weeks, the ocean retains information about its dynamical and thermodynamical state for significantly longer periods, thereby providing a basis for climate forecasts well beyond the weather prediction limit. Realizing this predictive potential, however, requires that the ocean's initial state be represented as accurately as possible at the start of a forecast.

The quality of seasonal forecasts is critically sensitive to errors in the ocean initial conditions. Biases in sea surface temperature (SST), sub-surface temperature and salinity structure, and sea-ice state at the start of a simulation can propagate through the forecast period and degrade prediction skill. In the Baltic Sea region, this challenge is particularly acute. The semi-enclosed basin is strongly influenced by freshwater input from rivers, air–sea heat exchange, and large inter-annual variability in ice extent, all of which must be captured faithfully for reliable seasonal outlooks. Systematic errors in model initial conditions arise from deficiencies in the atmospheric forcing fields, model parametrization, or from insufficient observational constraints, and must be corrected through data assimilation.

Data assimilation (DA) provides a statistically rigorous framework for combining model predictions with observations to produce an optimal estimate of the ocean state. A wide range of methods have been developed and applied in operational oceanography, from optimal interpolation and three-dimensional variational (3D-Var) schemes to ensemble-based approaches such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) and its localized variants (Evensen, 2003; Nerger and Hiller, 2013). Ensemble-based methods are particularly attractive for ocean applications because they provide flow-dependent, multivariate error covariances that correctly distribute observational information across correlated state variables and across all three spatial dimensions. The MOIRAI-DA utilizes the Parallel Data Assimilation Framework (PDAF, version 2.0, which includes the Localized

Error Subspace Transform Kalman Filter (LESTKF). This is an efficient member of this family that scales well to high-resolution operational configurations.

The MOIRAI project aims to develop improved ocean modelling and forecasting capabilities for climate risk assessment across European seas. Deliverable 2.2 addresses the improvement of initial conditions for the Baltic Sea component of MOIRAI. Building on the operational infrastructure of the Baltic Monitoring and Forecasting Centre (BALMFC) The MOIRAI-DA system assimilates additional observational data types — in particular, more in-situ observations, such as reprocessed Argo profiles, VOTO gliders, etc. This is beyond what is used in the standard operational configurations. The aim is to reduce initial condition errors and ultimately improve the skill of seasonal forecasts for the Baltic Sea region.

This report is structured as follows. Section 2.1 describes the model configuration and data assimilation methodology, including the NEMO 4.2 model set-up, the LESTKF filter configuration, and the observations assimilated. Section 2 presents result of the DA reanalysis experiment covering the year 2024, with validation against independent SST products and sea-ice observations from the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI). Section 3 evaluates the quality of the MOIRAI-DA initial conditions through a set of free-run experiments starting on 1 January 2025, comparing model trajectories initialized from MOIRAI-DA restart files against those initialized from the BALMFC operational Near Real Time (NRT) and Multi Year Products (MYP) systems as well as a reference run without data assimilation. The NRT product is the ocean forecast that is updated on a daily basis, whereas the MYP is the reanalysis. Both are published through the Copernicus Marine Services. Validation of the free runs is performed using Argo float profiles for both temperature and salinity over a five-month period, providing an independent, subsurface assessment of initial condition quality.

2. Data assimilation experiments for 2024

Figure 1 Model domain and position of additional observations assimilated during the MOIRAI-DA assimilation experiment. Panels show different data types with colors showing the observation date.

For this study, we replicated the BALMFC operational model setup using identical model code, boundary conditions, and operational atmospheric forcing from the Harmony atmospheric model. The Copernicus Marine Services, which BALMFC is a part of, offers two types of forecast relevant for the project. The Near Real Time (NRT) are daily updated forecast, whereas the Multi-Year Product (MYP) is a reanalysis that includes more data. The ocean model is based on a NEMO version 4.2 that includes the sea ice model SI³. The model employs a uniform regular horizontal grid with spacing of 1 nautical mile (approximately 1.7 km) and 56 unequally spaced vertical levels, with minimum spacing of 0.5 m at the surface increasing to a maximum of 25 m at depth. Figure 1 shows the BALMFC model domain, which covers the entire Baltic Sea and extends into the North Sea transition zone.

The data assimilation scheme is based on the Parallel Data Assimilation Framework (PDAF, version 2.0) (Nerger and Hiller, 2012). PDAF provides a wide selection of offline and online sequential filters based on various simplifications of the Kalman filter (Kalman, 1960). We employed the offline version of the Localized Error Subspace Transform Kalman Filter (LESTKF), consistent with the approach used in the BALMFC operational model. The LESTKF used in this study employs multivariate three-dimensional time-varying error covariances, calculated at each assimilation cycle from ensemble anomalies. These anomalies are derived from a 20-year historical simulation using a sliding temporal window of 14 days centered on the analysis date, yielding an effective ensemble size of 248 members.

The state vector consists of three-dimensional temperature, salinity, horizontal velocity components (u and v), and sea surface height (SSH).

The data assimilation scheme operates on a 12-hourly cycle, with the NEMO model paused at each cycle for calculation of analysis increments. All increments (temperature, salinity, velocity components, and sea level) are applied using the Incremental Analysis Update (IAU) scheme with a linear ramping function over a 12-hour window.

The assimilated observations dataset consists of the level 3S multi-satellite collated sea surface temperature from Copernicus Marine Data Store (SST_BAL_SST_L3S_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_010_032), sea ice concentration and thickness from FMI ice charts (SEAICE_BAL_PHY_L4_MY_011_019), and in-situ observations from the international council of exploitation of the sea (ICES - <https://www.ices.dk/Pages/default.aspx>), Monitoring stations and Tide Gauges (INSITU_BAL_PHYBGCWAV_DISCRETE_MYNRT_013_032), ARGO profiles, VOTO gliders and many more, aggregated specifically for this project. This constitutes the main difference in the assimilated observations between the current MOIRAI-DA experiments and the NRT system, since these observation types are not near-real-time, so they are not available when the BALMFC NRT system is running. The difference between the MOIRAI-DA and MYP system is also significant, since the reanalysis system is configured to assimilate the ice thickness observations.

3 Results and validation of the DA experiment for 2024

First, we assess the improvements in the ability of the MOIRAI-DA to correct the heat flux errors by assimilating the satellite sea surface temperature. Figure 2 shows maps of the centered root mean square errors (with bias removed) for four simulations: Reference (REF) run - no data assimilation, the MOIRAI-DA run, and the BALMFC MYP and NRT products. The centered Root Mean Square area is displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Maps of the cRMSE SST errors for REF, MOIRAI-DA, MYP and NRT experiments for the period 2024-01-2024-05. Top left reference, top right MOIRAI-DA, Bottom left Multiyear product, bottom right Near real time product.

The mean errors over the entire Baltic Sea area are 0.52, 0.41, 0.44 and 0.55 C correspondingly. Unfortunately, the BALFMC NRT product does not cover the North Sea, where the MOIRAI-DA experiment also shows good improvements.

The spatial distribution of SST errors reveals distinct regional patterns. In the open Baltic Sea, the MOIRAI-DA run reduces errors throughout the domain, with the largest improvements concentrated in the central Baltic and the Gulf of Riga, where stratification is most sensitive to accumulated heat content biases. The BALMFC MYP product

achieves comparable overall skill to MOIRAI-DA, reflecting the benefit of its multi-year reanalysis approach, while the NRT product — operating with a shorter assimilation window - shows higher errors, particularly in the southern Baltic. The reference run without data assimilation consistently exhibits the largest errors in all sub-regions, underscoring the essential role of DA in constraining the initial ocean state.

In addition to SST, we evaluate the sea-ice variables of the simulation for the 2023–2024 winter season. Figure 3 shows the time series of ice extent and ice volume for all four experiments compared against the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) ice charts, which serve as the primary observational reference for Baltic Sea ice.

Figure 3 Ice extent and ice volume for the 2023-2024 ice season compared against FMI ice charts.

The ice extent in the REF overestimates the ice extent in the sea ice growth season, as well as predicts higher peak values in January and March. MORAI-DA is doing

much better in this period. REF run keeps the ice better in the melting season, whereas MOIRAI-DA and NRT tend to melt ice too quickly.

The simulated ice volume of MOIRAI-DA is significantly better than both MYP and NRT and better than the NRT product.

Error! Reference source not found. shows maps of the maximum ice-covered area on 12 February 2024, near the seasonal maximum: the MOIRAI-DA experiment reproduces the observed ice distribution in the Gulf of Bothnia and Gulf of Finland most accurately among all configurations tested. Overall, the DA experiment demonstrates consistent improvements over the reference run for both SST and sea ice, validating the LESTKF assimilation scheme as an effective tool for constraining the Baltic Sea ocean state.

Figure 4 Maps of the maximum ice-covered area for observations, NRT, MOIRAI-DA and MYP experiments for 12th Feb 2024. Top left shows the observations, top right the near real time product, bottom left the MOIRAI DA product and the bottom right the Multiyear product.

4 Assessment of the initial conditions for the seasonal forecasts: free run experiment for 2025

The free runs were initialized with the restart files from the NRT system, the MYP system and the MOIRAI-DA restart files on 20250101. All the experiments have the same atmospheric forcing and boundary conditions. The experiments only differ in the initialization conditions.

We start again by assessing the heat content errors. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the SST bias errors for January 2025, which is after one month of the simulation.

Figure 5 Monthly mean SST bias for January 2025 for free runs started from REF, MOIRAI-DA, MYP and NRT initial conditions. Top left shows the reference, top right the MOIRAI-DA, bottom left the MYP product and the bottom right the NRT.

The simulation started from the restart files of the REF run has, as expected, the largest errors, with both large positive bias in the Gulf of Finland and the South-Eastern part of Baltic Sea, and large negative bias in the Kattegat and the North Sea. The free run, initialized with the MYP restart shows a similar pattern of the errors, with slightly lower magnitudes of the bias. The free run initialized from NRT restart shows significant

negative bias in the entire Baltic Sea. The free run initialized from the MOIRAI-DA restart files (top right panel) show consistently lower bias errors.

Next, we assess the MOIRAI-DA free run against the INSITU observations, namely Argo profiles and moorings. **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.** show time series of the bias and centered Root Mean Square Error (cRMSE) for temperature and salinity for the period 2025-01 – 2025-05.

Figure 6 Time series of temperature bias (top) and cRMSE (bottom) for free runs started MOIRAI-DA against ARGO profiles.

Both temperature and salinity biases stay low for the entire 5 months of the simulations and average cRMSE below 0.6 C for temperature and 1.0 psu for salinity.

These results compare favorably with free runs initialized from the REF, MYP, and NRT restart files. Only the MOIRAI-DA runs are shown. The run initialized from the REF restart diverges from observations most rapidly, with temperature biases exceeding 1°C and salinity biases above 1.5 psu by March 2025 in some depth layers. The NRT-initialized run, despite showing a large negative surface bias in January (**Error! Reference source not found.**), partially recovers over subsequent months as surface heat fluxes constrain SST,

but subsurface salinity errors remain elevated throughout the evaluation period. The MYP-initialized run performs somewhat better than REF and NRT, but still exhibits larger biases than the MOIRAI-DA-initialized run, particularly in temperature between 40 and 80 m depth where the Baltic halocline interacts with the seasonal thermocline.

Figure 7 Time series of salinity bias and cRMSE for free runs started MOIRAI-DA against ARGO profiles.

The vertical structure of the errors is displayed in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.** (only MOIRAI – DA run).

Figure 8 Monthly mean temperature bias (top row) and cRMSE (bottom row) vs depth calculated for free run initialized with MOIRAI-DA with respect to ARGO profile observations. From left to right month January, February, March, April and May.

Temperature biases remain well constrained throughout January and February for the upper 125 meters, with absolute values generally below 0.3°C. The bias increases in the lower part of the water column. The reason for this is to be investigated. From March onward, both positive and negative surface biases develop due to accumulated errors in the atmospheric forcing rather than deficiencies in the initial conditions. Importantly, sub-surface temperatures below 20 m depth - which represent the oceanic “memory” most relevant for seasonal predictability — remain accurately reproduced throughout the five-month period, with cRMSE values consistently below 0.5°C. Salinity vertical profiles show a similar picture: biases at depth remain small and stable, while near-surface variability increases in spring as river runoff and precipitation introduce freshwater that is not perfectly captured by the atmospheric forcing.

Figure 9 Monthly mean salinity bias (top row) and cRMSE (bottom row) vs depth calculated for free run initialized with MOIRAI-DA with respect to ARGO profile observations. . From left to right month January, February, March, April and May.

Figure 6 - **Error! Reference source not found.** show that the results of the free run initialized with the MOIRAI-DA initial fields are robust and can be used in further studies on seasonal and decadal predictability.

5 Concluding remarks

This deliverable presented the development and evaluation of a data assimilation system for the Baltic Sea within the MOIRAI project framework. The primary objective is improved initial conditions used for seasonal climate forecasts. Two main sets of experiments were carried out: a DA reanalysis covering 2024 and a set of free-run experiments initialized on 1 January 2025.

The MOIRAI-DA demonstrates clear improvements in SST accuracy relative to the reference run without assimilation, reducing the domain-averaged centered RMSE from 0.52°C to 0.41°C. The MOIRAI-DA experiment also outperforms the BALMFC NRT product (0.55°C) and is competitive with the BALMFC MYP reanalysis (0.44°C) while additionally providing improved coverage over the North Sea transition zone. The sea-ice evaluation for the 2023–2024 winter season confirms that the MOIRAI-DA correctly captures both ice extent and spatial distribution, with the maximum ice area on 12 February 2024 being reproduced more accurately than in any of the alternative configurations.

The free-run experiments initialized from the MOIRAI-DA restart files on 1 January 2025 demonstrate that the improved initial conditions translate into better ocean state estimates over the subsequent five months. Validation against Argo float profiles shows that temperature cRMSE remains below 0.6°C and salinity cRMSE below 1.0 psu throughout January–May 2025, with the MOIRAI-DA-initialized run outperforming all alternative initializations at subsurface depths. The vertical profile analysis confirms that the sub-surface temperature and salinity structures, which represent the oceanic memory most relevant for seasonal predictability, are accurately maintained over the evaluation period. The development of near-surface biases from March onward is attributable to accumulated atmospheric forcing errors rather than deficiencies in the initial conditions.

Taken together, the results demonstrate that the MOIRAI-DA data assimilation system provides significantly improved initial conditions for Baltic Sea seasonal forecasts compared to operational alternatives. The MOIRAI-DA restart files are therefore suitable

as a high-quality starting point for further studies on seasonal and decadal predictability in the Baltic Sea region, as planned in subsequent MOIRAI deliverables.

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